

Tax Morale and Personal Income Tax Compliance Behaviour in Kurmin-Mashi, Kaduna

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Abstract

This study addresses the issue of tax compliance behaviour in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna. The compliance behaviour has been very low which has in turn adversely affected the revenue of the state. This study examines the effect of tax morale on personal income tax compliance behaviour in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna. The population consists of 144 self-employed businesses that registered with the Kaduna State Internal Revenue Service and resides in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna. Yamane (1964) formula was used for sample size determination. Data were collected through questionnaire while descriptive statistics and regression analysis were used to analyze the data. The study finds that good governance, tax equity and fairness have positive significant relationships with level of taxpayers' compliance. The study recommends that government should sustain good governance and ensure tax equality and fairness.

Keywords: personal income tax, tax compliance, tax morale.

1. Introduction

Government expenditure increases on a daily basis as it tries to meet up with responsibilities owed to citizens. This has prompted government finding means of increasing its revenue base. Tax is one of the surest platforms through which government can generate revenue to discharge its social, economic and political programmes (Torgler, 2007). Tax provides revenue for government to invest in development, deliver public service, relieve poverty and build social and physical infrastructures for long-term growth (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2013).

Tax is seen as one of the vital sources of revenue generation to the government. It is an important revenue generating area in the sense that when other revenue generating areas fail, government can always fall back on tax sources. Tax is a compulsory contributions imposed by government on the income, salaries, wages, profits, gratuities of persons and public institutions or organizations (Kornhauser, 2007).

There is always an estimated tax revenue and actual tax revenue collected by the tax authority at the end of every year. The difference between the estimated and actual figure of tax revenue, according to Kornhauser (2007), is called the tax gap which he argues that it is largely caused due to non-compliance to the relevant provisions of the tax laws caused by tax avoidance and tax evasion. Diverse reasons had been put forward for the non-compliance to relevant provisions of the tax laws by tax payers. Kornhauser (2007) argues further that the decisions to comply to the provisions of tax laws is a rational issue but moral issues such as social norms, personal values and cognitive processes. This simply suggest that tax compliance is affected by personal and social norms like relating to procedural justice, believe, trust in the legitimacy of government. He further suggests that

full compliance is achievable by tax administrators when tax morale is incorporated into their operational framework.

The concept of tax morale offers suggestions about the tax payer's personal decision on whether and to what extent they evade taxes (Torgler, Schamffner, & Macintyre, 2007). Tax morale is seen as the intrinsic motivation to pay taxes. Torgler (2002) and Fred (2003) stress the relevance of tax morale to achieve high level of compliance to relevant tax laws. Several factors are key in understanding tax morale, such factors as equity, fairness and relationship between tax payers and government, cultural norms, trust in government and change in government polices (Fred, 2003).

Compliance is defined as the degree to which taxpayers comply with tax laws and administration without the actual application of enforcement activity (Andreoni, Erard, & Feinstein, 1998). Tax compliance could also be viewed in terms of tax evasion and tax avoidance. According to James, Murphy and Reinhart (2005), tax compliance is complying with the spirit of tax laws. Quite a lot of people find it uninteresting to pay taxes particularly those who are self-employed, owing to the fact that it helps to reduce their income level and the gross mismanagement by government in the use of tax revenue. Likewise, majority of the business men and women lack the knowledge of accounting that will help them keep appropriate records for the purpose of profit determination. As a result of this, they end up paying higher taxes because the tax authority uses best of judgment on them since their profit cannot be determined. Based on this ground, the tax payers are discouraged to pay their taxes. It is on this ground that this study examines the effect of tax morale on tax compliance.

There are several literatures on tax compliance behaviour in Nigeria. For instance, studies such as Akintoye (2013), Akowe and Awaje (2016), Chucks and Anthony (2013), Fakile (2011), Olamide and Segun (2015) were conducted in Nigera. However, they were conducted outside Kaduna State which is the focus area of this study. Mustapha (2016) examines the determinants of personal income tax compliance in Kaduna State, however, the study did not consider the very domain of this study which is Kurmin-Mashi where major business activities are carried out indicating a huge potential revenue generation.

The objective of this study, therefore, is to examine the effect of tax morale on personal income tax compliance in Kurmin-Mashi. In this light, the study hypothesizes that tax morale has no significant impact on personal income tax compliance in Kurmin-Mashi. This study is an emerging area of relevance and is timely as the tax authority is seriously campaigning on the need for tax payers to comply with tax laws. This study provides useful information to revenue collecting authority and thereby improving on tax compliance. However, the study is limited to self-employed business men and women who registered with the Kaduna State Internal Revenue Service and reside in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna.

2. Literature Review

Alm (1992), Lewis (1982), Roth, Schwartz and Witte (1998) and Schwartz and Orleans (1997) opine that tax morale is the intrinsic motivation that tax payers have to pay tax. Tax morale is also seen as the reason for tax compliance. Schmolders (1960) sees tax morale as an integral and important attitude that is related to tax compliance. Braithwaite and Ahmed (2005) define tax morale as the perceived internalized obligation of tax payer to

pay tax. According to Alm and Torgler (2006), it is the intrinsic motivation to pay tax liability or due tax.

Tax compliance is the degree to which tax payers comply with tax laws and administration which can be achieved without the actual application of enforcement activity (Adreoni, Erard, & Feinstein, 1998). Tax morale places emphasis on tax payers' internal motivations, social norms, cognitive process, personal values and sense of moral obligation to pay tax. Tax morale can equally be seen as an avenue to eradicate tax enforcement. This study adopts the definition given by Alm and Torgler (2006) because it is on the issue of motivation which is seen as the catalyst to increase compliance behaviour.

Sociology and psychology stressed the importance of behaviour based on moral and ethical considerations. In economic analysis, internalized values are taken as exogenously given and not influenced by prices or regulations (Becker, 1968; Hirshleifer, 1985). However, Hirschman (1965) and Sen (1977) took the relationship between external and internal motivation into account. Frey (1997) demonstrates that intrinsic versus extrinsic motivation are also relevant for explaining compliance behaviour. He looks at tax morale as a particular kind of intrinsic motivation. It is an attempt to introduce a psychological effect into economics without giving up the rational choice framework. His approach includes a crowding out effect of intrinsic motivation in the analysis of tax compliance.

Increasing monitoring and penalties for compliance, individual will notice that extrinsic motivation has increased, which on the other hand crowds out intrinsic motivation to comply with taxes. Thus, the net effect of a stricter tax policy is unclear. If intrinsic motivation is not recognized, taxpayers get the feeling that they can as well be opportunistic. This puts into account the relevance of policy instruments in supporting or damaging the intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation depends on the application of policy instruments. Frey (1997) claims that tax morale is not expected to be crowded out if the honest taxpayers perceive the stricter policy to be directed against dishonest taxpayers. Regulations which prevent free riding by others and establish fairness and equity help preserve tax morale.

Alabede (2012) states that good governance is concerned with authority in the public sector and even how the society organizes its affairs and manages its resources. Likewise, the World Bank (2006) views good governance as the ability of the government to effectively manage its resources and implement healthy policies for the benefits of all the citizens and institutions that regulate economic and social interaction in the country. Expressing the relationship between good governance and tax compliance, Everest, Philips and Sandall (2009) confirm that there is a nexus between good governance and tax compliance. They further suggest that the quality of governance guarantees good compliance behaviour. Therefore, a better provision of public social amenities or infrastructures by the government to the citizens as benefit to be enjoyed for paying their taxes may motivate the citizens to willingly comply with tax provisions.

It is reasonable that taxpayers develop interest in what government executes in terms of meaningful projects (Alabede, 2012). Everest, Philip and Sandall (2009) examine the activities of the government, particularly, those who pay high amount of tax. This high amount of taxes discourages them from comply with tax laws; especially if they perceive

that the government is not judiciously utilizing the tax revenue. Compliance behaviour is however quite difficult in self-employed system than the pay as you earn (PAYE) which according to Lewis (1988) has a larger opportunity to under report their income and therefore pay less tax. Kim (2008) concludes that non-compliance is influenced by price control, public service, collected corporate tax, gross domestic product (GDP) per capita, tax system which are the composition of government spending on the welfare of citizens.

Also, Richardson (2008) examines the determinants of tax compliance across 47 countries including the USA, the UK, Argentina, Thailand, Canada, Chile and Brazil and finds that government has a significant positive impact on determining attitudes toward tax compliance. Richardson (2008) suggests that government should improve its reputation and credibility in order to obtain trust and confidence from taxpayers.

In addition, Torgler (2004) establishes a significant positive relationship between the perception of the benefit to be derived from good governance and the willingness of taxpayers to comply with tax laws. In the same view, Fakile (2011) suggests that there is a high correlation between tax compliance and good governance. This implies that good governance positively encourages compliance. It is therefore safe to say that provision of infrastructural facilities and other public goods by the government has the tendency of motivating the citizens to comply with the provisions of tax laws.

Furthermore, Kasum, Abu-Kasum and Osemen (2013) find that bad governance and corruption reduces the level of compliance behaviour of tax payers. It is necessary to have in mind that the role of government in effective utilization of tax revenue has a direct influence on tax payers' level of compliance, especially those in self-assessment system (Richardson, 2008).

Tax equity and fairness are principles of taxation that encourage equitable distribution of tax liability. This principle provides a platform by which tax payers pay their taxes based on their level of income. Chau and Leing (2009) suggest that tax administrators and taxpayers' growing dissatisfaction with the equity and fairness level of the tax system is a major factor militating against tax compliance level. This position has been argued by different scholars in different dimensions. For example, Porcano (1984) finds that taxpayers' need and ability to pay are the most significant variables related to perceptions of fairness of the tax system.

Other surveys conducted by Scott and Grasmick (1982) and Spicer and Lindstedt (1976) conclude that respondents who believe that the tax system is unfair are more likely to commit non-compliance behaviour. Also, Bojuwon (2010) examines the impact of tax fairness on tax compliance in Nigeria. The study employs general fairness, exchange with government, tax structure special provisions and self-interest as measures of tax fairness. The study finds that only exchange with government and special provision out of the five fairness measures are accepted.

Likewise, Palil and Mustapha (2011) examine the perception of tax equity and fairness from a survey of 1,073 respondents. The results suggest that tax fairness has a significant impact on tax compliance. Also, Tehulu and Dinbem (2014) investigate the determinants of tax compliance behaviour in Ethiopia. In the same vein, Mukhlis, Utoro and Yuli (2014) argue that tax compliance can be built on the operation of tax fairness in the society. Likewise, Halil and Ahmed (2014) submit that unfair tax system discourages compliance.

3. Methodology

This study is on tax morale and personal income tax compliance in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna. The population consists of 144 self-employed businesses that are registered with the Kaduna State Internal Revenue Service and operate in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna. The sample size is 103 obtained using Yamane (1964) formula as adopted by Fakile (2011) and Mustapha (2015).

Tax morale is the independent variable while tax compliance is the dependent variable. The independent variable was measured using good governance, tax equity and fairness and peer group influence. In order to effectively capture the relationship between tax morale and personal income tax compliance in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna, the following model was specified:

$$TCDIR_i = \alpha + \beta_1 GG_i + \beta_2 TEF_i + \beta_3 PGI_i + \epsilon_i$$

Whereas:

TCDIR = Tax Compliance Score

α = Intercept

β_1 - β_3 = Beta coefficients of independent variables

GG = Good Governance

TEF = Tax Equity and Fairness

PGI = Peer Group Influence

ϵ = Error term

i = No of respondents

Table 1

Variables and their measurement items

Variables	Measurement items	Sources
Tax Compliance	-Accurate report of tax liability - Registering with tax authority voluntarily -Timely filing of require returns -Maintaining all require accounting records and other records -Payment of accrued taxes on time	Mustapha (2015) and Kircher (2007)
Good Governance	- Assurance of security - Trust in government -Satisfaction with the level of developmental projects	Mustapha (2016), Samuel (2011) and Alabede (2010)
Tax Equity and Fairness	- Computation of tax liability - Ambiguity in tax laws -Progressive distribution of tax liability	Bojuwon (2010) and Mustapha (2016)
Peer Group Influence	-Emulating friends -Consultation with friends -Listening to friends advice	Palil (2010) and Mustapha (2016)

Source: Author's Compilation (2018)

4. Results and Discussion

Although 103 copies of the questionnaire were administered, only 95 copies were filled and returned. The descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Information on good governance

Statement	NO	S-D & D (%)	NEU (%)	A & S-A (%)	MEAN	SD
Government uses tax revenue to finance infrastructural projects	95	45(47.3)	10(10.6)	40(42.1)	3.526	1.319
The government have been able to provide a very friendly business environment	95	8(8.4)	20(21.1)	67(70.5)	3.347	1.235
The government is on top of security issues and they is no cause for fear	95	12(12.6)	5(5.3)	78(82.1)	3.305	1.185

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From Table 2, it can be observed that the taxpayers did not agree in strong terms that the government uses tax revenue to provide infrastructural facilities. Whereas the people strongly affirm that the government has been able to provide a very friendly business environment and security situation in the state is under check or control. The opinion of the taxpayers thus suggests that the government is providing good governance. The mean score > 3.0 and standard deviation > 1.0 validate this position.

Table 3

Information on tax equity and fairness

Statement	NO	S-D & D (%)	NEU (%)	A & S-A (%)	MEAN	SD
Tax liability is imposed in a progressive manner that is equity in tax administration	95	80(84.2)	10(10.5)	5(5.3)	3.673	1.095
The administration of tax by tax officials is fair	95	52(54.7)	26(27.4)	17(17.9)	3.357	1.2625
It is very difficult to understand and interpret the tax laws	95	54(56.8)	6(6.3)	35(36.9)	3.557	1.217

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From Table 3, the opinion of the people show that there is no equity and fairness in tax administration and that the taxpayers lack the ability to understand and interpret the tax laws. Their positions are very strong as it is far > 50% and validated by the mean and standard deviation scores of (>3 & >1) respectively.

Table 4
Information on peer group influence

Statement	NO	S-D & D (%)	UD (%)	A & S-A (%)	MEAN	SD
I always pay tax when my friends pay theirs	95	68(71.6)	14(14.7)	13(13.7)	3.610	1.196
I often listen to my friends advice on tax issues or matters	95	44(46.3)	23(24.2)	28(29.5)	3.400	1.206
My friends attitudes towards paying their due taxes motivate me	95	28(29.5)	8(8.4)	59(62.1)	3.505	1.375
I always rely on my friends advice when compiling my tax returns	95	10(10.5)	8(8.4)	77(81.1)	3.44	1.173

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From Table 4, the taxpayers' response indicates that >70% pay their tax as their friends pay. However, on tax issues and matters, they did not agree in affirmative terms that they listen to friends' advice. Over 60% and 80% affirm that friends attitude motivate them and during tax returns compiling, they listen to friends' advice, respectively. The position of the taxpayers shows that 50% of the times they are influenced by friends and 50% of the times they are not. As usual, the mean and standard deviation justify these positions.

Table 5
Information on Compliance

Statement	NO	S-D & D (%)	UD (%)	A & S-A (%)	MEAN	SD
Accurate report of tax liability	95	16(16.8)	18(18.9)	61(64.3)	3.400	1.266
Registering with tax authority voluntarily	95	48(50.5)	4(4.2)	43(45.3)	3.725	1.161
Timely filing of required returns	95	75(78.9)	18(18.9)	2(2.2)	3.673	1.170
Maintaining all require accounting records and other records	95	63(66.3)	3(3.2)	29(30.5)	3.536	1.218
Payment of accrued taxes on time	95	16(16.8)	7(7.4)	72(75.8)	3.631	1.321

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From Table 5, >60% of the taxpayers says that they report their tax liability accurately. Also >50% suggests that they do not engage in voluntary registration and 78%

do not file their returns on time. 66% agree that accounting records and other records are not maintained. Meanwhile, 75% agree that they pay their accrued taxes on time. The validity of these positions is indicated by the mean and standard deviation score of (>3 & >1).

Table 6
Reliability Test (Cronbach's Alpha)

Average interitem covar	No of items	Scale reliability coefficient
0.181	4	0.7067

Source: STATA Outputs

From Table 6, Cronbach's Alpha is 0.7067, which is about 71%. The standard scale reliability coefficient is 70% and above. Thus, 0.7067 which is interpreted as 70.67% tested on the four items show that the questions have internal consistency to solve the problem of this study.

Table 7
Regression Results

Ind.Var.	Coef.	Std. Err.	t-statistics	P> t	VIF
GG	0.266	0.082	3.24	0.002	1.67
TEF	0.239	0.086	2.77	0.007	1.54
PGI	-0.102	0.090	-1.13	0.263	1.12
CONST.	2.203	0.345	6.38	0.000	
R	= 0.540				
R-square	= 0.292				
Adj R-square	= 0.285				
F-statistics	= 9.07				
P-value	= 0.000				

Source: STATA Outputs

From Table 7, the adjusted R² is 28.5% which indicates the variation in the level of tax compliance as explained by the independent variables. The p-value of 0.000 is considered statistically significant based on the fact that (p<0.05), an indication that the regression model is fit and as such, the study rejects the null hypothesis and therefore accepts the alternative hypothesis. In order to determine the presence or not of multicollinearity, Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was employed and the results indicate clearly that all the values of VIF are (<4) which is the stated standard, indicating the absence of multicollinearity.

Also, from Table 7, good governance results ($\beta_1 = 0.266$, $t = 3.24$, $p = 0.002$) indicate a significant positive relationship between good governance and tax compliance. This implies that good governance is a motivating tool that can bring about voluntary compliance. This finding is consistent with the findings of Palil (2010), Olamide and Segun (2015) and Mustapha (2016). Tax equity and fairness results ($\beta_2 = 0.239$, $t = 2.77$, $p = 0.007$) indicates a positive and significant relationship between tax equity and fairness and

tax compliance. This result implies that equity and fairness in the distribution of tax liability positively influences voluntary tax compliance. This finding is consistent with the findings of Tehulu and Dinberu (2014) and Edward, Mbekomize and Ifezue (2014).

Furthermore, peer group influence results ($\beta_3 = -0.102$, $t = -1.13$, $p = 0.263$) shows an insignificant negative relationship between peer group influence and tax compliance. This means that friend's attitude and advice does not increase tax compliance level. This finding is consistent with the finding of Akintoye (2013).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the impact of tax morale on personal income tax compliance in Kurmin-Mashi Area of Kaduna. This is considered essential in order to fill the gap that has been established in the literature on tax compliance. Data were collected by administering questionnaire on 103, however, only 95 respondents filled and returned the questionnaire. Descriptive statistics and multiple regression technique were employed to analyze the data. From the findings, it can be concluded that good governance, tax equity and fairness strongly enhance tax compliance in the area. However, peer group influence does not influence voluntary tax compliance.

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the study recommends that government should judiciously utilize tax revenue in providing public goods to taxpayers. This could be in form of engaging in developmental projects, standard infrastructural facilities and provision of security. In addition, the tax authority should ensure equity and fairness in the distribution of tax liability.

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